

**MULTIMEDIA AND COMMUNICATION OF AFRICAN HUMAN
MIGRATION NARRATIVE OF THE 2017 CARNIVAL CALABAR
OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA: A SYNOPTIC AND
PICTORIAL INTERPRETATION**

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Abstract

This paper analyses Carnival Calabar's adoption of various media (multimedia) to frame a narrative on themes with special focus on the 2017 Carnival Calabar theme (African Human) Migrations. The complexity that accompanies the coordination of various media texts used for transmitting narratives in Carnival Calabar is the problem to be unraveled. This paper examines the problem of multimedia as a means of communication within the framework of the Media Framing and Play theories of the media. The paper adopts the analytical research method. Five (5) synopses of the five (5) competing bands and eight (8) pictures taken from the 2017 Carnival Calabar are randomly selected and used as units of analysis in this paper.

Findings from the analyses of the bands' synopses and pictures indicated that the African human migration narratives from the point of peaceful settlement of African communities to invasion by the foreign nations and voyages to the western world for slavery were an actual reflection of history of human migration in Africa. Findings also showed that the use of multimedia attracted an unusual interest from the audience, evoked feelings of pains and pity for Africans who suffer as victims of migrations. The paper recommends a coordinated use of multimedia in carnivals and other performing arts for communication of themes to the audience.

Key Words: Carnival Calabar, Framing, Human Migration, Multimedia, Narrative

Résumé

Cet article vise analyser l'adoption par le Carnaval de Calabar des divers médias (multimédia) pour encadrer un récit des différents thèmes avec l'accent sur le thème du Carnaval de Calabar de 2017 sur la migration humaine. La complexité qui accompagne la coordination des différents textes médiatiques utilisés pour transmettre des récits durant le Carnaval de Calabar est un mystère à éclaircir. Cet article examine le problème du multimédia comme moyen de communication dans l'encadrement des théories médiatiques et du rôle des médias. L'article adopte l'approche de recherche analytique. Cinq (5) scénarios des cinq (5) groupes en compétition et huit (8) photos prises lors du Carnaval de Calabar en 2017 sont sélectionnés au hasard et utilisés comme unités d'analyse. Les résultats des analyses de ces scénarios et images des orchestres montrent les récits de migration humaine en Afrique du point de vue du règlement pacifique des différends communautaires en Afrique, ce qui est préféré à l'invasion des nations étrangères pendant les voyages vers le nouveau monde durant l'esclavage. C'est une représentation réelle de l'histoire de la migration humaine en Afrique. Les résultats ont également montré le fait que l'utilisation du multimédia a suscité un intérêt exceptionnel de la part du public, ainsi que des sentiments de douleur et de pitié pour les Africains qui souffrent en tant que victimes des migrations. L'article recommande une utilisation coordonnée du multimédia dans les carnivals et autres spectacles pour la communication des thèmes au public.

Mots clés : Carnaval de Calabar, encadrement, migration humaine, multimédia, narration

Introduction

Popular carnivals all over the world, from Trinidad and Tobago, the Caribbean, and the Brazilian to the Nottingham have deployed several media forms or platforms to communicate themes to their audience. The combination of these media forms as a systemic channel of communication appears to be less appreciated than the messages they convey yet Marshal McLuhan insists that “the medium is the message”. The concept of multimedia is often misconstrued by modern scholars. The use of the term has also been limited to the use of computers hooked unto some audio and video devices and projected unto a screen. Marshall (2001), for instance, defines multimedia as an application which uses a collection of multiple media sources e.g. text, graphics, images, sound/audio, animation and/or video.

In reality, multimedia forms for transmitting information involve any combination of literary, technological and performing arts. Belavadi (2013) defines multimedia production more succinctly as the presentation of a message using a combination of spoken and written words, music, moving and still images, graphic animations, infographics and hyperlinks, Thus, in the performing arts such as the carnival, the adoption of visual platforms (pictures, drawings, artistic carving and designs), audio channels (musicals, supportive oral narration and sound effects) and other performance and media platforms such as drama, dance (choreography), models, costumes, transit media, engraved signs, floats, written signs, human media has attracted scholars’ interest in re-examining the term ‘multimedia’.

In the context of Carnival Calabar, the multimedia channels adopted are largely based on the yearly themes. According to Udoka, Ememchukwu and Affiah (2020), Carnival Calabar themes since inception include *Carnival Queen (2005)*, *Our Beauty, Our Culture (2006)*, *celebrating our Heritage through culture (2007)* and *sustaining Earth’s Treasurer through our Heritage (2009)*. Others are *Our Strength and Resilience; The Bedrock of our Future (2010)*, *Endless Possibilities (2011)*, *Celebrating a New Dawn (2012)*, *Ain’t No Stopping Us (2013)*, *Climate Change (2016)*, *Migration (2017)*, *Africanism (2018)* and *Humanity (2019)*. Generally, the multimedia communication in Calabar Carnival assumes several dimensions such as reveling, dramatization, acrobatics, magical displays,

dance, musicals, floating, costuming, and many other human and technological forms.

At the turn of the 21st century, the Carnival Calabar was initiated as an annual event celebrated in a unique way. The spirit of reveling has been with the people, and this form of traditional theatre hitherto served the social function of exercising some level of control on social behaviours (Essien 2005) but the Carnival Calabar road march flagged off in the year 2005 when the state conceived the idea of taking advantage of the innate culture of warmth of the people to drive the Carnival vision to a commercial success. The Carnival events have grown in popularity, scope and participation year in year out. Today, it is arguably Nigeria's strongest tourism brand, including the street parties, musical concerts featuring both international and local artistes, 12 kilometer floats and parades of five competing bands and several non-competing bands from within and outside Nigeria, Children's Carnival, Drama, African Cultural Carnival Parade Day featuring traditional dancers and masquerades from different parts of Nigeria and Africa, and the beauty pageant activities. These support Essien's (2003) position that the performing artist plays a significant role of presentation and preservation of the human artistic excellence in the society.

The Bikers Carnival was recently introduced to add international vent to the events, while the green carnival became part of the party for awareness creation on the need for conserving the environment for humanity and future generations. Various themes for the carnival since inception hinged on the issues of history, resilience in Africa, hope in Africa, immigration concerns and environmental conservation to mention a few. The Carnival Calabar experience in the 21st century can be considered as worthwhile for raising awareness on environment and migration issues rocking the world now.

In terms of development, the Carnival Calabar has created jobs in the areas of tailoring for costumes, (a development that culminated to the setting up of the Calabar garment factory by the present administration), bead-making, weaving, carnival shoes and choreography. . Essien (2008) opines that business and art managers should pay attention and understand the imports of their work on the environment This has also empowered more

women in their quest for independence and freedom as observed in Gloria Eme Worugji's "Redefinition of the position of women in Osonye Tess Onwueme..." that women no longer sit at home doing nothing but have engaged themselves in other activities that enhance their status in the family and society at large (180) During the carnival enactment, the streets become busy, buying and selling soars, accommodation in hotels are taken; photographers are engaged as people tour areas of interest in the city. Taxi operators and hair salons are patronized round the clock as the city never goes to sleep. In fact, the socio-economic development of Cross River State is already enticing enough to woo other Africans wishing to migrate to foreign countries to have a rethink. To those in Diaspora, it is an event for cultural reconciliation; a blend of costume, dances and a showcase of cultural heritage. In 2017, the Carnival Calabar was focused on reflecting on a crucial world issue, human migration.

Human migration, the movement by people from one place to another, with the intention of settling permanently or sometimes temporarily in a new location, has attracted the attention of the world as a topical discourse, owing to the contemporary exigencies of the 21st century. On a rather unfortunate note, Adams (2015) reports that more than a million migrants and refugees from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq and other countries such as Pakistan, Eritrea, including Nigeria, crossed into Europe, sparking crises as countries struggled to cope with the influx and the task of resettling people.

Citing the International Organization for Migration (IOM)'s reports, the United Nations High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR) (2020) reports that the 21st century has witnessed the highest levels of migration in history and by 2019, the number of migrants reached an estimated 272 million, 51 million more than in 2010. The report also indicates that international migrants comprise 3.5 percent of the global population. Compared to 2.8 percent in 2000 and 2.3 percent in 1980, the proportion of international migrants in the world population has also risen. The unprecedented number of migrants around the world has been forced out of home due to some natural disasters or man-made conditions including socio-economic activities within their respective environments; among them are refugees who are under the age of 18. The plight of migrants in the 21st Century has

opened our eyes to the fact that the environment can be friendly yet most unfriendly to man.

The environment, considered as a sum total of surroundings of a living organism, natural forces and socio-cultural or economic and political circumstances of life of people, has provided conditions for development and growth as well as of danger and damage. The activities of man and his natural environment result in a situation where nearly 20 people are forcibly displaced every minute as a result of conflict or persecution.

It is glaringly logical that any environment bereft of the necessary peace, allowing for conditions that will force people to migrate to other locations, is deprived of development – a state of economic and social transformation based on complex cultural and environmental factors and their interactions. This is demonstrated by Walter Rodney (1972)'s book: *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa*. The parochial treatment of development issues can be detrimental to posterity, but suffice it to state that development in this context is considered more as achieving that state of economic and social transformation than the systematic use of scientific and technical knowledge to meet specific objectives or requirements.

The Narrative of African Human Migration has assumed Multi perspectives; the African and the Non-African. Both perspectives have degenerated into two schools of thought; the Africans who believed that the Europeans forcefully shipped them to Europe and America for slavish exploitation of their human resources and non-Africans who believe most Africans voluntarily undertake migrations to Europe and America in search of greener pasture. African migration is definitely an issue today irrespective of existing perspectives. According to Dunn (2019), that demographic imbalances, economic inequality and increased globalization including political instability and climatic changes are responsible for an estimated 1 billion migrants in the world today.

More than a decade ago, Kohnert (2007) posited that 18% of all African migrants in 2005 were refugees, citing reasons for Africans' migration to Europe to include unemployment, violent conflicts, gross human violations, population pressure, degradation of natural resources, poverty and the quest to search for greener pastures. Understanding the realities of African Human Migration goes beyond accepting the causes as advanced

by narrators who are far from those who actually experienced the phenomenon – the Africans. An African Historian, Imbua (2011) reflects on African Human Migration issues, particularly, the dehumanizing aspect and manner with which it occurred in his book *Across the Atlantic*. The narrative platforms, observably, are moldings or drawings, prose, drama, poems or a combination of some. Little narratives on African Human Migrations exist on the platform of performing arts. Few films such as Wolper (1977)'s *Roots* and Amata (2006)'s *Amazing Grace*, have attempted a performance of a part of dehumanizing process of African migrations, yet there are more contemporary aspects of the story that appear undocumented and the carnival arts is one of them.

The objective of this discourse is to identify the multimedia platforms used in the 2017 execution of the theme of migration and frame them into a synchronized narrative on African human migration from the perspectives of the Carnival Calabar competing band leaders. The key question in this discourse is how these media were used to frame the African migration narrative in the 2017 Carnival Calabar. Significantly, the outcome of this discourse will visibly display outdoor performing media channels available to Directors and encourage other band leaders to adopt as many and necessary media forms as they can to prosecute future themes in the Carnival. The method employed in this study is the analytical research method while the synopses of all the competing bands will be adopted as units of analysis.

The 2017 Carnival Calabar Experience and the Presentation of Migration Theme

Cambridge Dictionary (nd) defines carnival as a special occasion or period of public enjoyment and entertainment involving wearing unusual clothes, dancing and eating and drinking, usually held in the streets of a city. The Macmillan Dictionary (2021) defines carnival as a lively festival in which people walk through the streets playing music, dancing, and often wearing unusual colourful clothes. Carnivals are characterized by performances, hence their categorization as performing media or arts.

In 2017, the Carnival Calabar, an emergent street medium and performing art platform, held as usual, this time with an interesting focus on 'migration.' According to Akpan (2018), the Governor of Cross River State, Professor Ben Ayade, during the 2017 Miss Africa contest which was one of the features, expressed the need for integration of the African continent and urged Africans seeking greener pastures abroad to return home and help build the continent, describing as futile the excessive desire of young Africans to migrate through Morocco, the Mediterranean Sea, the Sahara desert and all the difficult routes to land in Liberia just to end up as slaves. The Governor's words were only an echo of his reason for choosing the theme of 'migration' for reflection in the Carnival Calabar of 2017. The objective was also obvious; to discourage African human migration by informing, educating and creating awareness about the negative effects of African human migration to Nigerians.

With the proposed introduction of more festival properties, including the beach soccer competition, the 2017 Carnival Calabar looked even more promising. With regards to the environment and migration, the Carnival Calabar has reconciled displaced cultures with attractive features such as the Ekpe Masquerades, whose roots would have been lost in myth and mystery on the other side of the globe, amongst our brothers from Southern America. The event has given opportunities to more than 15 foreign countries to participate as at 2015. During the newly introduced international carnival event, there were appearances by Brazil, Belize, Mexico, Indonesia, Italy, Croatia etc; countries from Africa, Asia, Europe and America (North and South). The promotion of cultural interactions has been enormous, thereby strengthening the process of the global village in a dramatic dimension. The artistic communications on exotically designed floats transmit more words in advising Africa and the world on the need to remain environmentally conservative.

Udoka, Enemchukwu and Affiah (2019) state that the five competing bands in the Carnival Calabar are Bayside Band, Freedom Band, Masta Blasta Band, Passion 4 Band and Seagull Band. For the 2017 edition of the carnival, all the bands keyed into the theme of 'migration' and gave it different interpretations and performances from the African point of view. Common among their narratives was the point that African human migration from the onset began with deliberate destabilization of the peacefully and communally inhabited African communities through

diplomatic approaches, exploration, and instigation of communal wars, followed by the voyages into the slave world, colonization and finally neo-colonization. How the theme of ‘migration’ was interpreted and the various media employed to communicate the theme remains the major focus of this discourse. The bands adopted various media which has birthed the multimedia discourse.

Multimedia and Framing Techniques in Carnival Calabar

There are various categories of media namely modern/technological media, new media, African traditional media, human media, transit media, electronic media, print media, transit media, outdoor media and many more depending on their nature and functions. Haralambos and Holborn (2008) generally group them into three categories: technological media, organizational media and human media. Technologically based media refer to channels of communication characteristically made up of technologies, including radio, television, internet and mobile phones while media as organizations refers to media houses. People are human media when they serve as platforms for transmitting information to an audience. Multimedia message are framed using a mix of media channels such as signs, printings, paintings, dances (human based), musicals and many more.

Lake and Karen (2004) define multimedia as a broad term that applies to the integration of text, graphics, sound, video and animation into a document such as a letter, brochure, newsletter, webpage or presentation. Ike (2005) defines multimedia similarly as the use of text, graphics, animation, audio or a sequential use of a variety of materials (platforms) or transmission of information. Both definitions imply that multimedia involves the adoption of more than one channel of communication at a time to present an organized narrative. Thus, multimedia is the use of combined media channels for a presentation of live or documented information.

Africa's Environmental Conditions for Migration

To understand the growing concerns of Africa's environment and migration crises, one needs to glance at the crystal ball of migration history in Africa and the natural and social environmental forces that wrote the history. History records that in the 1860s, at least 12 million Africans were forcibly taken to the America – then known as the “New World” to European settlers. This largest forced migration in human history relocated some 50 ethnic and linguistic groups. The unfortunate and forced migration of Africans at that point was orchestrated by the activities of the Europeans and some African slave merchants who sought to enrich themselves at the expense of human lives. Communal wars, betrayals and the quest to satisfy some economic and social well-being were some of the reasons behind these acts.

When slavery was abolished in 1865, the black populations, specifically African Americans, were the largest number of migrants in the world. History has christened the phenomenon “The Great Migration”. Many scholars consider the period between 1916 and 1930, and 1940 to 1970 as an era that witnessed the migration of a total of six million African Americans from Northern America to the South. The major reason was to search for jobs. The last decades of the 20th century marked a new migration trend; African American migration to the South grew tremendously. The two biggest reasons for this trend were for familial ties and economic betterment. African Americans sought greatly to re-unite with their folks and re-integrate culturally.

Since 1960, a period that stems the post-industrial era, emigration from Africa, Asia and Latin America has increased dramatically. In addition to traditional immigrant receiving nations in Oceania and the Americas, countries throughout Western Europe, notably Germany, France, Belgium, Switzerland, Sweden and the Netherlands now attract significant numbers of immigrants. Most African migrants tend to originate from nations with less developed economies. Scholars have tied Africa's migration to continuous search for economic well-being, higher wages in developed countries overseas and African's displacement in the course of economic growth.

Analytically, one can posit that Africa's migration is driven essentially by social, economic and political forces of African's environment, namely poverty, conflicts, natural environmental factors and other crises, as in Liberia, Sierra Leone, Togo and Cote d'Ivoire who experienced crises in the recent past. Existing views on reasons for Africa's migration also include demographic, economic, ecological and political factors, including deteriorating living conditions, environmental degradation, widening economic inequalities and lack of long-term peace and security. In addition, poor governance, nepotism and corruption, human rights violations, political instability, real or perceived opportunity for a better life, need for higher income, greater security, and better quality of education and health care of the destinations. Lower cost of migration, improved communication, greater information availability and familial are additional environmental reasons.

By the beginning of the 21st Century, environment and international migration and their relationship with development became the most pressing issues on the contemporary global agenda. For instance, net migration rates for 2016 show that about 50 percent African migrations were to Northern America, Europe and Australia. The African experience in the 21st century can best be summarized as postulated by the findings of Crush, Peberdy and Williams (2006):

- i) Africans have experienced migration as a necessary endeavour to situate themselves within the international labour market and to earn a better livelihood.
- ii) More than 50 million migrants in the world are from African countries including Cote d'Ivoire, South Africa, Somalia, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Ghana, Senegal, Cape Verde, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Mali, Gambia and Zimbabwe.
- iii) Internal African migrations involve men, women and children and include rural-rural, urban-rural and urban-urban flows as well as rural-urban movements.
- iv) Internal migration appears to have been influenced more by economic crisis and structural adjustments.

- v) African migrations to Europe and United States in the 21st century are predominantly of educated individuals, giving rise to considerable concern over the issue of 'brain drain'.
- vi) In relation to brain drain, the development of the health sector in Africa has been affected by the migration of doctors and nurses, even through regional migration flows (South Africa, Namibia and elsewhere).
- vii) Most African migrants to developed countries are not really enjoying better living conditions or jobs.
- viii) Most African migrants do not get to their desired destination; they lose their lives on the sea or in the desert, go hungry while some die in the process from severe illness, while others who reach their dreamlands after years of suffering are repatriated.
- ix) Most African migrants today are victims of xenophobic attacks (in South Africa and elsewhere).

Summarily, the development implication for the African experience in the 21st century include mass export of economic manpower from Africa, gradual and sustained erosion of African cultures and promotion of unfavourable global economies for Africans.

Theoretical Framework

The basic propositions of this discourse are the multimedia abilities to frame a narrative and the Carnival Calabar's ability to communicate messages effectively. The Media Framing Theory and the Play Theory are therefore adopted to support these propositions. According to Ike (2005), Anthropologist Gregory Bateson was credited with first positing the Media Framing Theory in 1972. The theory holds that media channels package and present information or highlight certain events and then place them within a particular context to encourage or discourage certain interpretations. Thus the Media Framing Theory refers to the general way a news medium treats a topic or how messages are encoded with meaning so that they can be efficiently interpreted in relation to existing beliefs or ideas. In the context of the existing discourse, the Media Framing Theory supports the power of multimedia to present a narrative on African human migration from the context of the experience of Africans and their media Directors. The frames are carefully selected in forms of different media and

used to reinforce the African human migration story in a systematic or correlative manner as it occurred overtime, giving the narrative a direction.

The play theory on the other hand was developed by William Stephenson in 1967. According to Ike (2005), the mass media, under the play theory, are seen as pleasure-oriented. Their primary function is to allow the audience to escape work and to enjoy themselves while decoding the message. In this context, the Carnival Calabar and all the media platforms, deployed to communicate the theme of African human migration comprise various media platforms such as drama, music, dance, artistic designs, costumes and floats, with the intent to entertain the audience while making them to understand the messages of communal living, dislodgement of African settlements, communal wars, slave voyage and mass migrations.

Synoptic Analysis

Bayside Band

Her Excellency, Mrs. Onari Duke is the Bayside band's leader. The band's colour is blue. The summary of the band's position on African migration was "the grass isn't always greener on the other side." The band adopted the transit media (allegoric trucks), sculptures, drama, dance and human media. The dramatic medium reflected on once peaceful African community while transit medium conveyed the slave master's slip that berthed on the shores on African. Also, drama was used as a medium for narrating, the meeting of the African chiefs and the "white men", and how the African chiefs betrayed their kinsmen. The human media form was used to convey the message of African slaves in chain and the costumes helped to press home message. The sculpturing work was adopted to design the set where slaves were exposed to suffering and abuses on the plantation. The latter part of the narrative, using the same media, showed the return of African Americans whom other Africans envy and sacrifice all they have to migrate to America.

Freedom Band

Dr. Iyam Ugot is the Freedom Band's leader and the band's colour is yellow. The key message as captured on a handbill was titled "The Memoir of Kassiba." Though the use of the term "Kassiba" was fictional, it was used to describe the beautiful and green vegetation of Africa and the love,

peace and harmony that bound the Africans in brotherhood. The band's narrative explained through media and dramatization to show that major reasons for African human migrations to Europe are corruption, nepotism, social collapse, insecurity and criminality. These according to the band's narrative, are the reasons for the voluntary African migration.

Other factors for voluntary African migrations narrated were unfolding chaos, lack of electricity, water, good roads and other social amenities; epidemics, floods, erosion, pollution and malnutrition. The human media was used to show how Africans cross the Sahara on foot while sculptures were used to show the camels and Africans' ordeal in the desert areas. The band used models of plane to show Africans' quest for flight to developed countries, and the slave ship for forced migrations. The band also adopted the use of models to show bicycle as means of transportation used even across the desert.

Masta Blasta Band

Led by a Senator of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Senator Gershom Basse, the Masta Blasta, represented by the orange colour, used the human media dramatization, dance, sculptors and transit media to transmit the message that Africa's migration to developed countries is more will-full than forced. The narrative held that wars, oppression, genocide, disease and economic strangulation are some reasons for African's migration to Europe and America. From the band's summary "Masta's Pastures," the band states that Africans migrate in search of liberty, dignity, prosperity, amity and fulfillment.

Passion 4

Honourable Chris Agibe, a member of the House of Representatives in Nigeria, is Passion 4's band leader. The colour of the band is green. The band employed transit media, dance/dance drama, human media, models, sculptors and carved images of two black birds (Africans) who flew away (migrated) in search of greener pastures. The African dancers were the human media used to portray the celebrative and peaceful mood of African geographical landscapes before the advent of the slave masters.

Forced flight of Africans occasioned by draught and famine, poor political leadership and violence, unemployment narratives were told using human

media, dramatization and standard signs. The same media were employed by the band to tell the stories of legitimate migrants and illegitimate migrants from Africa who attempt to cross the Sahara, who end up in Libyan jails or as modern Libyan slaves; how others are used as organs of harvest and how others die at the Mediterranean Sea in attempts to cross over to Europe. The band also used floats and signs to show how African migrants finally make it to developed countries and end up as “brown patches on green lawns” with menial jobs such as street sweepers, dish washers, taxi drivers, sex workers, yahoo boys, bar maids, strippers, morgue attendants, door men, and many more. The story continues however that some legal migrants who go abroad for studies return as Architects, Engineers, Neurosurgeons, Nurses, entertainment workers and many more.

Seagull Band

The Seagull Band is led by a former Distinguished Senator of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Princess Florence Ita-Giwa. The colour of the band is red. The title of the band’s theme on migration was “Odyssey”. Major media employed for use were human media, transit media, print media, signs, and dramatization. The band’s story on migration follows domestic settlement of Africans, arrival of Europeans traders, the slave trade phenomenon characterized by torture and resistance, conflict and war (the Bakassi experience) and the fate of sex workers of African extraction in Libya and Europe.

Pictorial Analysis

The above picture is a shot that depicted the costumes of African slaves who were dressed in sack clothes and saddled with metal chains around their necks and leather anklets on their hands. The pictorial medium communicates the trauma and agonizing faces of Africans who were captured to be taken into slavery. The medium also shows the frustration and helplessness of the slaves at that time. The slaves were mostly victims of communal wars waged by Africans themselves. Their forced movement to Europe was therefore based on human more than natural or economic reasons.

The slave ship in the above picture was constructed and floated by Freedom band as part of the narrative. The ship is a representation of the vessel of slavery that conveyed African slaves on a voyage from the shores of Africa to Europe. This picture has a documentary value and is educationally significant to most young audience members or onlookers who may not have had an opportunity of citing the sight of the slave ship despite few narratives in history lessons. The model ship as captured in this picture was applauded by the carnival audience. Most of them took pictures of the ship, an indication of interest in the use of various media and communication approaches in narrating the story of human migration from Africa.

The airplane in the picture was also constructed and paraded the Freedom band. Apart from the reflection of great, innovative and artistic display of creative talent, the constructed airplane was also a symbolic representation of a vessel of slavery, this time not of early and forceful slave movement but voluntary migration of Africans from Africa to Europe in search of greener pasture. The picture presents to us that great technological innovations in transportation such as the airplanes, engine-driven vessels and cars are some of the secondary factors aiding human migration from Africa to Europe.

The picture of a bevy of young ladies was intended to display mere Africa costumes for ladies during the pre-slavery era in some parts of the continent. Before the slave trade era, African ladies were gorgeously dressed with the native combs on their hair and with bracelets and beads on their bodies adorning the local fabrics. Significantly, this picture justifies the pictorial medium of communication as a preserver and transmitter of history and depicts pictures as media of infotainment.

The picture above captures traditional dancers, presenting Ugep cultural dance in Cross River State as was represented by one of the competing bands, Seagull Band. The dancers are dressed in local costume depicting

one of the African communities. The chalk-marks on their bodies are also significant to certain beliefs held by the Africans. Most importantly, the dance steps, which are not visible and motional as a result of one of the shortcomings of the still picture medium, are depictive of the typical African scenarios of celebrations before the advent of the slave masters. The celebrative mood captured in the picture shows the peaceful nature of co-existence that was inherent among the African communities before the initiation of forceful migration – slavery – by the Europeans.

The designed shield in the picture represents the mean and fiercely looking faces of African warriors, who themselves are shown holding the shield and getting ready for battle. The picture reminds one of the uneasy battles among Africans as propelled by the Europeans. Historically, the European slave merchants could not move into the hinterlands to capture slaves. They gave gifts of dry gin, mirrors and Dane guns to the African war lords in exchange of slaves. The mode of transactions propelled the war lords to wage wars with neighbouring communities so as to capture more slaves and get more gifts from the Europeans. The picture above is therefore part of the narrative with more history behind the scene than presented.

The significance of the picture above in the 2017 Carnival Calabar is to further demonstrate the plight of the African slaves and the emotions of pity that accompanied it. The picture represents the King of Seagull Band who himself (human media) is a slave in chains. The artistic carvings, drawings and paintings are creatively positioned to show frustration, anger, ribs on the chest as a result of emaciation from hunger and blood stains from injuries inflicted on the slaves at the point of capturing. The representation is also educative and informative to the carnival audience in the sense that they get to see the models of history on human migration in Africa apart from reading them.

The images of hungry-looking, malnourished children pictured in the above excerpt is another angle of the African human migration narrative that shows the present human conditions (hunger, diseases and wars) that constitute major reasons why people are migrating from Africa to other parts of the world. The conditions are quite pitiable. The same conditions are reflected in the lives of Africans who end up trying to migrate to Europe and America; who end up as refugees and who are mercifully granted amnesty to live in some countries with better living conditions.

Discussions of Framed African Human Migration Narratives

The multimedia platforms used in the 2017 Carnival Calabar by the various bands aided the framing of narrative on African human migration in various ways. From the foregoing, the African communities were made up of peaceful settlements during the pre-colonial era. Africans enjoyed the atmosphere of good neighbourliness. Drama was the major medium used to express this assertion. The advent of the colonial masters, as corroborated by renowned African historians was a rude shock to the Africans. First, the narrative from the carnival presented the colonial masters as people who came to Africa as spies (explorers), then second as forceful slave masters.

Although the dramas could not re-enact the explorers' advent in detail, the representation of how the early Europeans penetrated the shores of Africa and deceptively sought the attention of Africans through various gifts as mirrors and dry gin were succinctly captured through the synopses of each competing band. The narrative indicated that Africans were indeed gullible and naive; they were quick to reacting to selfish instincts by promptly accepting the gifts from the unsuspecting European slave merchants at that time.

Apart from the gullibility of Africans at that time, further narratives showed that some Africans had insatiable quest for wealth. This was evident in their betrayal of their kinsmen; their roles as middlemen in the slave trade saga. The early African costumes aided the portrayal of true early Africans who were always half clad, dressed in animal skin or sack clothes while the ladies carried unique African hair-styles and adorned their bodies with native beads and bangles. These attributes have been captured and reflected pictorially. The multimedia use of drama, synopses, pictures and many more, to communicate the narrative on African human

migration also indicated that African communities were united through traditional dances, local songs (ballads) and traditional wrestling contests. Africans' lifestyles were those of communal living, happiness and contentment.

The destabilization of the once united Africa by the Europeans and their instigation of Africans against Africans and how they captured Africans as prisoners and victims of communal wars were all demonstrated in dramatic, synoptic and pictorial forms with the aid of costumes and other property as guns, gin and other property. This is a justification that the use of multimedia communication was an avenue to reinforce the narrative on African human migration and to support the existing history of problems of migration from African perspectives.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Multimedia Communications is considered in this paper as the use of more than one medium (songs, music, pictures, drama, speeches, dance, and drawings) to support the transmission of a message to the audience. The use of the term multimedia has been limited by many scholars to mean the utilization of computers and other accompanying appliances to communicate to an audience. That corrected, this study examined the use of multi-media in the 2017 Carnival Calabar on the theme African Human Migration. The synopses (written medium), dramas and selected pictures used in executing the themes by different competing bands were examined. This study concludes that the understanding of the synopses and artistic presentations of the bands on African migrations was supported by other media such as drama and pictures (multimedia) to help communicate the message on African human migration effectively. The interest demonstrated by carnival audience was indicated by their coming out to witness the multimedia and their taking of pictures. The use of multimedia communication is therefore appreciated by the audience anywhere, especially for achieving efficacy in communications targeted at information and education. This study recommends that all artistic performances should employ the use of multimedia for effective transmission of messages to the audience. The study also recommends that leaders of carnival bands in a competitive atmosphere should adopt the use of more multimedia communications in order to excel.

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